

ONLINE BUSINESS VENTURE TOOLS, AND STRATEGIES: ITS USE, VULNERABILITY, AND SURVIVAL FOR A BUSINESS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to analyze the use, vulnerabilities, and survival of microbusinesses who engage in social media. However, some criticalities in the use of social media, especially connected to limitations to accessibility, representativeness capacity, and the risks of disinformation and surveillance, have emerged and need to be further investigated also how it can be used as a tool for resilience by vulnerable businesses. In particular, the research also focuses on the uses that displaced vulnerable businesses have to deal with in post-pandemic settings that occurred in the two districts of the province of Surigao del Sur. Vulnerability is not always regarded as an admirable characteristic. Social marketing theory seeks to combine marketing ideas, principles, tools, tactics, and socially beneficial concepts to improve the resistance and susceptibility of firms using social media. This study had 438 respondents and employed a descriptive quantitative research method. It's interesting how social networking sites, regardless of platform, are employed in online business to allow firms to communicate with others, share, and produce content through communities. Businesses use social media to communicate in a variety of ways, including films, live streams, postings, photographs, and posts from customers who have already patronized the business with related notes. It is a great business tool. It is extremely beneficial in spreading the business's products, services, and brand, and it provides every business with the opportunity to delight and captivate clients online at a significantly lower marketing cost.

Keywords: *Vulnerability, Survival, Online Business, Strategies, E-Commerce*

INTRODUCTION

In today's technologically-equipped world, social media has arisen as a marketing tool for micro-enterprises engagement in online business, bringing people together and streamlining communication. According to Forino (2015) In today's modern settings, innovation and the technology-driven world in complex marketing adopting social networking sites has become an avenue where retailers can extend their marketing campaigns to a wider range of consumers as a "connection between consumers to the marketing world offering a diversified network for user-centered networking and social interaction. It is extremely beneficial to all types of enterprises and entrepreneurs and has gained popularity in recent years.

However, according to Kelley D.,et.al (2019) all social media networks, exposes businesses to the broadest audience and have the most extensive set of commercial options of any social network. According to Ibrahim and Aljarah (2018) The phrase "social media" refers to new media strategies that incorporate communication among individuals or groups of people. Social networking services enable individuals or groups to communicate, and microbusinesses might benefit from them. Businesses can make their marketing more appealing to all customers by utilizing social media sites like Facebook, TikTok, Instagram, and others. According to Parashar (2023), using Facebook for your small business may seem difficult because the platform's policies and algorithms change regularly. Despite the frequent challenges, the use of efficient approaches makes Facebook the finest social media platform for businesses. It gives you access to a specific audience, allowing you to communicate with customers and grow your online audience.

According to Debashish and McQuenn. (2012) also claims that Facebook is in the business of small businesses, with over a million businesses using this program every month to build virtual shops and reach customers, with millions relying on it to help them transition online since the pandemic began. Bianchi and Andrews (2015) believe that despite the problems individuals face and beyond, Facebook will continue to do everything it can to help them survive and, hopefully, prosper online. This research is essential because it will shed light on why social media is such an effective marketing tool for microbusinesses. As mentioned Mehay and Bowman (2005) Understanding its use, challenges, and potential informs researchers and microbusiness owners how to better use social media as a marketing tool for microbusinesses and reach out to their target clientele using social media. Furthermore, this study will contribute to the present body of information on this topic, benefiting future generations.

Research Questions

The principal purpose of this study was to determine the vulnerability and survival rate of the use of social media in online businesses in the Province of Surigao del Sur by emerging entrepreneurs. notwithstanding the role of microbusinesses in the Philippine economy as the basis for the study. In particular, it tried to address the accompanying inquiries.

1. What is the type of online business engaged in online business using social media platforms in the Province of Surigao del Sur?

2. What is the profile of the respondents?
3. What are the uses of social media for microbusinesses?
4. What is the degree of vulnerability of social media to microbusinesses?
5. What is the perceived survival rate of social media in microbusinesses?
6. What is the significant relationship between the respondent's profiles and the vulnerability encountered by microbusinesses?

METHODOLOGY

The research participants were registered micro- and small-business owners from the Province of Surigao del Sur, which consisted of the two districts that were engaged in and actively conducted business on social media. The statistical treatments utilized in this study included frequency counting, which was used to determine the frequency of respondents' responses to the demographic profile. The weighted mean was used to calculate the counted replies to each indication and to interpret the responses, while Pearson product-moment correlation was used to quantify the link between the respondent's profile, vulnerability and survival and the tests encountered. The researcher instrument utilized an adapted survey questionnaire from the research of Montenegro, et.al 2024. The instrument was organized into four parts. Each component of the questionnaire was answered using a 4-point forced likert scale. The study took a quantitative research approach. The primary data collection technique used in the study was a questionnaire. The questionnaire data was analyzed using descriptive statistics before being synthesized and processed to produce the results. The study's findings were presented in tables to make them more readable. Furthermore, this study employed a quantitative research design to gather numerical data and provide objective interpretations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 Types of Online Businesses Engaged in Online Business Using Social Media Platforms

Type of Online Business	District 1	District 2	Total	Rank
Live Selling	123	143	266	1
Digital Marketing	72	43	115	3
Virtual Assistant	17	21	38	7
E-Commerce	62	36	98	4
Fashion and Clothing Live Selling	67	71	138	2
Advertising Business	11	19	30	9
Affiliate Marketing	17	14	31	8

Food Online Delivery	19	26	45	6
Handmade Good Product	3	5	8	12
Merchandising	21	39	60	5
Bookkeeping	3	4	7	13
Consultant	14	8	22	10
Online Talent	9	9	18	11
TOTAL	438	438		

Table 1 presents the responses from all respondents from the two districts of the province of Surigao del Sur, Philippines using purposive sampling. According to the data, the most significant business is live selling, followed by digital marketing. The least common online business practice in the province is bookkeeping.

Surigao del Sur, officially known as the Province of Surigao del Sur, is a Philippine province in Mindanao's Caraga area. The capital is Tandag City. Surigao del Sur is located on Mindanao's eastern coast and faces the Philippine Sea to the east. As of 2020, the total population was 642,255. This accounted for 22.90% of the total population of the Caraga region, 2.45% of the Mindanao island group, and 0.59% of the total population of the Philippines. According to these numbers, the population density is 130 inhabitants per square kilometer or 337 inhabitants per square mile.

According to PhilStar, the 2019 Surigao del Sur Bank pioneered cloud technology in the Philippines. As more businesses around the world are told to innovate or perish, a small rural bank in this isolated municipality in Mindanao has adopted the use of cloud technology in its operations to overcome deficiencies and withstand the harsher regulatory environment. Like CanBank, one of Surigao Sur's rural banks has entirely transferred its core banking activities to the cloud service provided by Europe-based technology firm Oradian, eliminating the need for a physical data center in its head office. At the same time, the migration now allows the bank to dispatch tablet-bearing account officers to the distant reaches of the bank's service community to collect loans.

Following the pandemic, the Province of Surigao del Sur gradually increased its use of social media. The improvements were consistent in terms of innovation and social media marketing in offering products and services. It is clear that thanks to nearly 90% internet signal coverage and the availability of electric power in the area, it is now much easier for so-called modern entrepreneurs to conduct business via the internet.

Table 2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Age	Age Bracket	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
	15-20	19	4%	9
	21-25	29	7%	7
	26-30	44	10%	6
	31-35	63	14%	3
	36-40	67	15%	2
	41-45	78	18%	1
	46-50	55	13%	4
	51-55	50	11%	5
	56-60	22	5%	8
	61 above	11	3%	10
TOTAL		438	100.00%	
Sex	Category	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
	Male	157	35.84%	2
	Female	264	60.27%	1
	Lgbtq+	17	3.88%	3
TOTAL		438	100.00%	
Marital Status	Status	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
	Single	199	45%	1
	Married	154	35%	2
	Widowed	46	11%	3
	Separated	39	9%	4
TOTAL		438	100.00%	
Monthly Income	Amount	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
	Less than P50,000.00	79	18.04%	4
	P50,001.00 –150,000.00	57	13.01%	5
	P150,001.00 - 250,000.00	118	26.94%	1

	P250,001.00 –500,000.00	88	20.09%	2
	P500,001.00 – P1,000,000.00	82	18.72%	3
	1,000,001.00 and up	14	3.20%	6
TOTAL		438	100.00%	
Years in Business Operation	No. of years	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
	Less than 2 years	84	19%	3
	3-4 years	98	22%	2
	5-6 years	64	15%	4
	7-8 years	101	23%	1
	9-10 years	39	9%	6
	10 years and above	52	12%	5
TOTAL		438	100.00%	

Table 2 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of demographic variables among microbusiness owners, such as age, gender, marital status, monthly income, and enterprise operations. The bulk of responders are aged 41-45, with the highest rank and percentage of 18%. From the point of view of Carwford and Finn et al. (2015), individual-level factors influence organizations, and these interactions produce emergent, collective, and organizational-level outcomes, which may influence macro-level institutional determinants that generate gender disparities in entrepreneurs' growth goals. However, responders aged 61 and up have the lowest percentage and ranking.

The majority of respondents are female, with the highest rank and percentage of 60.27%, while Lgbtq+ has the lowest rank and percentage of 3.88%. In terms of marital status, the plurality of respondents (45%) were single, with 199 responses. According to Montenegro, D. (2023) In the field of doing business, there are estimations on the delivery of business services in terms of online use and control for selection resulting from business decisions. The size of the marital status and productivity effect shrinks but remains significant in most cases. The majority of single people want to start a business since they have the most free time in their lives. Separated ranked bottom (5.28%), As indicated in the study by Wilkin, J.,et.al (2019). In terms of monthly income, those with less than P150,001 pesos had the highest rank (26.94%), while those with more than ₱1 million and one pesos had the lowest rank (3.20%). In terms of company experience, 7-8 years obtained the highest rank and a percentage of 23%, while 9-10 years or more received the lowest rank and a percentage of 9%. Demographic research provides vital information on the microbusiness scene. According to Shabbir, M. S. et al. (2016), contributions to implementation provide an additional interpretive framework that reinforces the study's findings. According to Mehay & Brown (2005) this emphasis on

adaptive decision-making is congruent with the study's findings, which show that younger entrepreneurs use resources skillfully in uncertain conditions. The report recognizes women's significant contributions. Furthermore, the fact that nearly half of the respondents reported financial difficulties highlights the theoretical framework's usefulness in supporting a thorough understanding of demographic profiles and decision-making processes in microbusiness settings.

Table 3 Usage of Social Media for Microbusinesses

Indicators	Mean	Adjectival Rating
Social E-Commerce	3.91	Strongly Agree
Perceived Ease of Use	3.26	Agree
Satisfaction	3.73	Strongly Agree
Trust	3.23	Agree
Social Media	3.61	Strongly Agree
Perceived Usefulness	3.20	Agree
Socialization	3.64	Strongly Agree
Information Sharing	3.22	Agree
Over-all	3.48	Strongly Agree

The figures in Table 3 show that social commerce is the most highly ranked variable. According to Nasabi and Sujaya (2023), social commerce apps and online interactions have created new economic opportunities. This is mostly due to the proliferation of social networking sites, which has also led to the expansion of social e-commerce (mean 3.91), but perceived usefulness is the lowest-rated variable (mean 3.20, adjectival rating agree). This implies that the vast majority of respondents believe that social commerce provides considerable benefits to businesses, such as increased business growth, lower costs, better customer service, and expanded distribution channels. According to Liverman D., (1990) emphasizing social commerce as a valuable tactic in a variety of contexts. Social media is an important aspect of today's world. It helps users to stay connected and share ideas, thoughts, and opinions with others in a safe and secure manner. According to Welter, F., et.al (2017), the analysis seeks to extract and potentially apply the qualities of patterns seen in sales strategy and marketing, and it discovers that social commerce is viewed positively. According to the study's findings, microbusinesses strongly prefer the use of social media. Social networking is a wonderful way to link businesses and customers, resulting in reciprocal benefits. This reinforces respondents' positive attitudes toward social commerce, particularly in areas such as business growth and customer service.

Table 4 Vulnerability of Social Media to Microbusinesses

Indicators	Mean	Adjectival Rating
Diversification	3.74	Strongly Agree
Information Disclosure	3.28	Agree
Communication	3.71	Strongly Agree
Fake Accounts	3.27	Agree
Cost-Effective	3.72	Strongly Agree
Malware	3.14	Agree
Convenience	3.66	Strongly Agree
Time-Saving	3.56	Strongly Agree
Over-all	3.51	Strongly Agree

Table 4 shows that diversification is the most highly rated variable for social media vulnerability for microbusinesses, with a mean of 3.74 and an adjectival rating of strongly agree, while malware is the least rated variable, with a mean of 3.14 and an adjectival rating of strongly agree. This illustrates that respondents strongly agree on the importance of social media platforms in business. Currently, most online businesses are vulnerable to viruses or malware distributed via social media, which rely purely on chaotic activities enticing links to click and some appealing attachments of harmful code to friends to propagate the infection or its agent. While social media has altered the way we interact with people, when used maliciously, it has the potential to damage vulnerable people in society, whether that's through exploitation, harassment, or even possible identity theft. According to Mc Adam et.al (2019) , social networking can help you connect with your customers and discover what they are saying about your company. This is consistent with previous discussions about the benefits of social media for businesses. Exploring specific approaches that correspond to these perceived benefits may result in more successful organizational procedures and higher overall performance. Furthermore, more research into the distinct characteristics of social media usage in various businesses may shed light on specialized tactics for maximizing its conveniences and time-saving benefits. You can also utilize social media for marketing, promotions, and mobile apps. Broaden your market reach, including overseas markets. Increase revenue via customer networks and advertising.

Table 5 Survival of Social Media to Microbusinesses

Indicators	Mean	Adjectival Rating
Competition	3.11	Agree
Customer Conduct	3.15	Agree
Monitor Engagement	2.99	Agree
Marketing Campaign	3.10	Agree
Prices	2.83	Agree
Trust Issues	3.07	Agree
Customer Support	2.84	Agree
Product Information	2.77	Agree
Over-all	2.98	Agree

Table 5 reveals that the most-rated variable is customer conduct, with a mean of 3.15 and an adjectival rating of agree; the least-rated variable is product information, with a mean of 2.77 and an adjectival rating of agree. The overall mean is 2.98 based on the responses of the respondents for the survey of the businesses. The effective use of social media can help any business survive, but it will take some effort and planning. Moving with the fast-paced advances in online technology can help you improve your brand, raise your profile, and potentially win new customers. However, every entrepreneur must maintain a healthy perspective on what the company can invest in social media and what it can realistically expect in return. According to Crawford & Finn (2015) competition and marketing initiatives build and maintain consumer trust, which is now critical to retaining existing customers and attracting new ones. Good customer service is essential in every organization. According to Montenegro et al. (2024), customer service is critical since it serves as a direct link between your customers and your company. The consensus on adjectival evaluation suggests that micro-businesses have trust concerns on social media. According to Vagianos D and Koutsoupias, N (2017) It implied that people were aware of the issues with online platforms. It lends credence to the idea that consumers are beginning to understand the benefits and drawbacks of online shopping. Businesses that provide exceptional customer service can repay client acquisition expenditures, fostering positive word-of-mouth and a devoted following that refers new consumers.

Table 6 The significant relationship between respondents' profiles and the vulnerability encountered by micro businesses

VULNERABILITY					
Variable Tested		Computed r	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Variety	Age	0.156	0.300	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Sex	0.141	0.306	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Marital Status	0.043	0.736	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Monthly Income	0.209	0.229	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Years in Business Operation	0.181	0.288	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Communication	Age	0.144	0.362	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Sex	0.091	0.633	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Marital Status	0.153	0.327	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Monthly Income	0.188	0.228	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Years in Business Operation	0.087	0.591	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Cost-effective	Age	0.091	0.577	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Sex	0.103	0.519	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Marital Status	0.140	0.394	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Monthly Income	0.291	0.075	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Years in Business Operation	0.249	0.129	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Convenience	Age	0.038	0.852	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Sex	0.080	0.684	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Marital Status	0.079	0.583	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Monthly Income	0.267	0.109	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Years in Business Operation	0.111	0.483	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Time-Saving	Age	0.083	0.654	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Sex	0.118	0.473	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant

	Marital Status	0.226	0.158	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Monthly Income	0.221	0.159	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Years in Business Operation	0.049	0.764	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant

Table 6 summarizes the conclusions of the analysis conducted to determine the relationship between the respondent's profile and the opportunities encountered by microbusiness owners. The correlation coefficients (r) and p-values were determined for each of the opportunities' factors: variety, communication, cost-effectiveness, convenience, and time-saving. It found that, in terms of diversity, there is no significant relationship between the owner's opportunities and monthly income, with a maximum computed r of 0.141. Furthermore, the respondent's time savings over years of firm operation, with a computed $r = 0.0424$, show no relevant relationship with the owner. It did not reject the hypothesis for each variable. This suggests that age, gender, marital status, monthly salary, and number of years in business did not affect the prospects identified by microbusiness owners on social media platforms. The researcher determined that there is no significant relationship between these demographic factors and the identified opportunities because all p-values were greater than 0.05. According to Veluchamy et al. (2020), the appropriate use of social media has enabled entrepreneurs and startups to accelerate their businesses and make huge revenues. These results are consistent with Lambert's 2020 study, which found no significant association between the consumer profile and the owner or firm itself. Social media is often regarded as a versatile tool for adapting content and marketing businesses in response to changing customer needs and business circumstances. This suggests that the customer's changes do not affect either of these parties.

Conclusions

This information might be used to provide entrepreneurial and management advice or ideas to grow their business even on a low wage. Understanding these criteria allows us to provide better support for this group. Using a framework that views vulnerability as a dynamic feature in both physical and social contexts. This aids in assessing and discussing the vulnerability and survival opportunities that social media may bring in these situations. Social media provides opportunities for survival or to reconnect with people online. In the context of long-term relocation, social media has the capacity to reconnect people and organize engagement in community and physical place restoration.

It appears that social media can provide a "virtual space" to fill the gaps left in physical and social spaces as a result of pandemic calamities. The Province of Surigao del Sur only welcomed and shifted from traditional business to some of the enterprises during the pandemic, and it is now widely practiced. Furthermore, technology can be utilized to minimize the isolation to which some people, particularly minors, are subjected and to share their experiences with others in post-disaster situations. In this scenario,

minors cannot be limited to the state of vulnerability since they demonstrate resilience, and social media can help them in this regard. According to Montenegro, D., et al (2024) this underlined the perceived importance of social media in assisting with various corporate procedures and identified areas for development, particularly in terms of time savings. The study's findings revealed that, among the various aspects analyzed, social commerce scored the highest grade, but satisfaction with microbusinesses' usage of social media was the lowest. The study emphasizes the significance of social commerce for micro-businesses, as well as the necessity to address and increase satisfaction levels with social media use. This highlights the importance of working to build and maintain trust in the online platform. Meanwhile, the survey found that social media presents significant opportunities for microbusinesses, notably in terms of simplicity. Furthermore, while appreciating the benefits, microbusinesses encountered challenges on social media, with trust difficulties being the greatest. Customer service, on the other hand, had the lowest rating of any of the challenges, showing that it is not as widespread as other issues. On the other hand, the study discovered no significant relationship between the respondents' profiles and the chances available to microbusinesses. Similarly, no significant relationship was found between respondents' profiles and the challenges encountered by microbusinesses. According to Stieglitz et al (2018) this demonstrates that social media concerns may be common across demographics or are not caused by individual responder characteristics. According to Sanberg, S. (2021) This demonstrates that these opportunities are either universal or are not significantly influenced by microbusiness demography. Finally, the recommended strategy plan is named "Maximizing Usage for Microbusiness Growth by Leveraging Opportunities and Overcoming Challenges." This intervention tries to capitalize on opportunities while minimizing barriers.

Recommendations

The researchers highly suggest the following based on their observations and conclusions:

Based on the revealed demographic profile of microbusiness owners, it is recommended to help younger entrepreneurs (41-45 years old), with a focus on empowering women in micro businesses that sell online. Women are far better at nurturing the personnel that report to them, which can only improve the company's state and success by encouraging and motivating people within it. Women entrepreneurs are more broad and imaginative in their business fields, and they excel at the talents required in the business. Similarly, they provide an important representation of the economy in terms of consumer insight.

Live selling, fashion and clothes, and digital marketing are the most common types of enterprises in the province that use social media or operate online. These are superior to traditional firms since they may reach their target market in a more flexible manner in terms of location, standard working hours, and scalability.

The firms shown in the table by years in business are those that were established following the epidemic; some have been in operation for less than four years. It is true that the pandemic has had a negative influence on firms, such as increased costs, decreasing sales, and labor-related difficulties such as remuneration or retrenchment, but at the moment, it actually opens the doors to the newly emerging market in online selling. It truly provides hope and a better opportunity. The pandemic-induced digitalization was viewed as both a potential silver lining from the crisis, increasing long-term productivity, and a risk of greater labor market disparity between digital and non-digital workers.

Innovative solutions adapted to specific needs, as well as ongoing trend monitoring, are required to ensure optimal utilization and a competitive advantage. According to Zarpou et.al (2012) Create a regular and engaging online presence to build customer relationships and take advantage of the ease social media provides for microbusinesses. Given the widely acknowledged importance of trust issues on social media platforms for microbusinesses, businesses should actively address and alleviate these concerns. Create a feedback loop with customers via social media channels, allowing for immediate operational adjustments based on customer insights while increasing overall efficiency.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author states that there are no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work presented in this study. The researcher values human dignity and privacy, takes extra measures, and attempts to equitably spread the advantages and burdens of research.

REFERENCES

- Archana Parashar, (2023) Global Trends in Technology Startup Project Development and Management pp 171–183. DOI https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-40324-8_11 Print ISBN978-3-031-40323-1. Online ISBN978-3-031-40324-8
- Bianchi, C., & Andrews, L. (2015). Investigating marketing managers' perspectives on social media in Chile. *Journal of Business Research*, 68(12), 2552–2559.
- Crawford, K. and Finn, M. The limits of crisis data: analytical and ethical challenges of using social and mobile data to understand Disasters *Geojournal*, 80 (4) (2015), pp. 491-502
- Debashish Mandal, & Robert J McQueen. (2012). Extending UTAUT to Explain social media adoption by microbusinesses. *International Journal of Managing Information Technology (IJMIT)*, 4(4), 1 to 11. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3531482>
- Forino G., Disaster recovery: narrating the resilience process in the reconstruction of L'Aquila (Italy) *Geografisk Tidsskrift-Danish J. Geo.*, 115 (1) (2015), pp. 1-13

- Harrison, S., Johnson P. Challenges in the adoption of crisis crowdsourcing and social media in Canadian emergency management *Govern. Inf. Q.*, 36 (3) (2019), pp. 501-509, 10.1016/j.giq.2019.04.002
- Ibrahim, B., and Aljarah, A. (2018). Dataset of relationships among social media marketing activities, brand loyalty, revisit intention Evidence from the hospitality industry in Northern Cyprus. *Data Brief* 21, 1823–1828. Doi: 10.1016/j.dib.2018.11.024
- Kelley, D. J., Baumer, B. S., Brush, C., Greene, P. J., Mahdavi, M., Majbouri, M., Cole, M., Dean, M., & Heavlow, R. (2017). *Global Entrepreneurship Monitor women's entrepreneurship 2016/2017*. Available at <http://gemconsortium.org/>. Retr July 1, 2020.
- Lambert, B., Jerry (2020). The relationship between the Customer profile with the Business owner. 12, 23-35.
- Liverman, D.M. Vulnerability to global environmental change R.E. Kasperson (Ed.) *Understanding Global Environmental Change: the Contributions of Risk Analysis and Management*, Clark University (1990), pp. 27-44
- McAdam, M., Harrison, R. T., & Leitch, C. M. (2019). Stories from the field: women's networking as gender capital in entrepreneurial ecosystems. *Small Business Economics*, 53, 459–474. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-018-9995-6>
- Mehay, Stephen L. and Bowman, William R. *Southern Economic Journal* Vol. 72, No. 1 (Jul., 2005), pp. 63-77 (15 pages) <https://doi.org/10.2307/20062094> <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20062094>
- Montenegro, D. L. (2023). Business Prospects and Challenges of Micro Small Medium Enterprises in Tandag City Under the New Normal: Basis for MSME's Business Sustainability. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8218963>.
- Montenegro, Donald L. , Bolabola, Christine M. ; Lincones, Rhea Jane D. Pido, Beolita C. ; Ponlaon; Mary Grace E.. *Embracing Social Media as Business Marketing Tool: Its Use, Opportunities, and Challenges for Micro Businesses*. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)* DOI:10.47772/IJRISS <https://www.rsisinternational.org/journals/ijriss/>
- Nasabi , Afreen Nishat A., & Sujaya H. (2023). Social Commerce for Unbranded Products in India- A Case Study of MEESHO. *International journal of management, technology, and social sciences (IJMTS)*, 8(1), 213–223. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7697686>
- Philstar, reported by Czeriza Valencia Surigao bank pioneers cloud technology in the Philippines. September 16, 2019. <https://www.philstar.com/business/business-as-usual/2019>. Sanberg, S. (2021) Was a Challenging Year for Small Businesses. Retrieved from <https://about.fb.com/news/2021/02/2020-was-challenging-for-small-businesses/>
- Shabbir, M.S., Ghazi, M.S., Mehmood, A.R. (2016). Impact of Social Media Applications on Small Business Entrepreneurs. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 6(3), pages 3.
- Stieglitz, S., Mirbabaie, M., Fromm, J., Melzer, S., *The adoption of social media analytics for crisis management - challenges and opportunities* (2018, Research Papers 4 (n.p.))

- Vagianos, D. & Koutsoupias, N. (2017). Social Networking Influence and Popularity Index Analysis as an Online Marketing Tool. 9th Conference in Data Analysis, Thessaloniki. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10443390>
- Veluchamy Ramanujam, Nagarathinam Uma Devi, Kasilingam Lingaraja and Chellaswamy Dhayanand, Association Between the Profile of Respondents and Their View on Relationship Lending Among the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise Borrowers, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 11 (3), 2020, pp.475–487.<http://www.iaeme.com/IJM/issues.asp?JType=IJM&VType=11&IT>
- Welter, F., Baker, T., Audretsch, D., & Gartner, W. B. (2017). Everyday entrepreneurship: a call for entrepreneurship research to embrace entrepreneurial diversity. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice* 41(3), 311-321. 10.1111/2Fetap.12258
- Wilkin, J. E., Biggs, Tatem, A.J. Measurement of social networks for innovation within Community Disaster Resilience Sustainability, 11 (7) (2019), pp. 19-43
- Zarpou, T., Saprikis, V., Markos, A., & Vlachopoulou, M. (2012). Modeling users' acceptance of mobile services. *Electronic Commerce Research*, 12(2), 225-248.
-